

Hodo Abubakar

December 18, 2023

Understanding the Absence of Al-Shabaab in Somaliland: Factors and Implications

Somaliland, the oldest unrecognized state in Africa, emerged following Somalia's 1991 civil war.¹ It is a compelling subject for analysis due to its strategic location bridging the Houthis in Yemen along the coast and Al-Shabaab in southern Somalia, making it a crucial security study point. Beyond its geopolitical importance, Somaliland is an intriguing case study in rapid state-building post-conflict. It showcases a unique blend of governance, fused with the influence of the traditional clan system, intertwining the rule of law with cultural elements. This paper is going to analyze the significance of effective governance and the emergence or absence of militant groups.

The significance of this topic lies in its challenge to our understanding of terrorism fundamentals and its role in analyzing the emergence of extremist groups. This unique situation demands attention as the only case globally where a country split after a civil war. One part experienced a gradual rise of an extremist group as a coping mechanism and in exchange for governance, while the other integrated clan traditions with democracy, resulting in a peaceful government for 33 years. Exploring this scenario sheds light on environments conducive to terrorist groups, contributing to ongoing research on why these groups emerge in certain places. It may also aid in identifying characteristics that foreshadow such events.

¹ Egoshin, Alex. "Former and Current Unrecognised States in Africa." *Vived Maps*, vividmaps.com/former-current-unrecognised-states-africa/.

Therefore, the question I am exploring is the factors that contribute to the absence of an Al-Shabaab presence in Somaliland. I am addressing the question by first introducing the region and the events that led to the formation of Al-Shabaab by delving into Somalia, Somaliland, and Al-Shabaab's historical context. The paper will explore factors hindering Al-Shabaab's presence in Somaliland, such as governance, counter-terrorism efforts, and sociocultural aspects. I will discuss the factor of border control, with a focus on the Lasanod case. Additionally, I will analyze economic and international factors influencing the absence of Al-Shabaab. Lastly, I will wrap up with future prospects and address potential threats to Somaliland's peace, and the conclusion will summarize key points. The inability of Al-Shabaab to penetrate Somaliland can be attributed to a robust governance system involving community participation, swift military responses to threats, geographical separation between southern and northern Somalia, diverse economic means, and the distinct identity of Somalilanders, presenting significant challenges for Al-Shabaab's influence.

History and Origins of Al-Shabaab

Al-Shabaab, an Al-Qaeda affiliate, Sunni Islamic terrorist group briefly gained control of central and southern Somalia in 2011.² The group became formally recognized as a foreign terrorist group in 2008 by the US. Al-Shabaab targets foreign military forces, the Somali government and security forces, and civilian targets such as schools, shopping malls, universities, and busy intersections.³ Al-Shabaab has carried out mass-casualty operations in Kenya, Somalia, and Uganda, but has never conducted an attack outside East Africa.⁴ As of

²Somalia Situation Update: October 2023 | Al-Shabaab Strikes Back at Local Administrators." *ACLEDA*, 20 Oct. 2023, acleddata.com/2023/10/20/somalia-situation-update-october-2023-al-shabaab-strikes-back-at-local-administrators/.

³Foreign Terrorist Organization; Al-Shabaab." *National Counterterrorism Center* | *FTOs*, Dec. 2021, www.dni.gov/nctc/ftos/al_shabaab_fto.html.

⁴Ibid

December 2021, It was estimated that Al-Shaabab had up to 7,000 to 12,000 fighters, almost double the number it had three years ago.⁵ Al-Shabaab recruits foreign fighters from various regions including the Middle East, neighboring Somali communities, and Somalis residing in Western countries such as the United States, United Kingdom, Australia, and Sweden.⁶ Utilizing the internet they exploit grievances, glorify returning to Somalia, and often antagonize the West in their recruitment strategies.

Al-Shabaab emerged in the aftermath of the collapse of the government in 1991, following the Somali civil war. Before the civil war, Siyad Barre governed the country after assuming power through a coup in 1969.⁷ Barre, initially supported by the United States, severed ties with the Soviet Union and aligned with the West, receiving substantial aid, around \$100 million annually, until 1989.⁸ Despite his alliance with the West, especially the US, Barre advocated a form of scientific socialism based on Marxism-Leninism with a heavy influence on Somali nationalism.⁹ His downfall began with ill-advised decisions, such as declaring war on Ethiopia in pursuit of unifying greater Somalia, which alienated all his international support.¹⁰ In addition, the country, under his regime, faced severe human rights abuses, the United Nations Development Programme described it as "one of the worst human rights records in Africa."¹¹ These abuses include the Isaaq genocide, which claimed 50,000 - 60,000 lives and was a catalyst

⁵"Al-Shabaab Whetting Sword near the Border of Ethiopia." *Hiiraan*, 22 Nov. 2023, www.hiiraan.com/news4/2023/sept/192990/al_shabaab_whetting_sword_near_the_border_of_ethiopia.aspx.

⁶Omenma, J. T., et al. "Al-Shabaab and Boko Haram: Recruitment Strategies." *Peace and Conflict Studies*, no. 10827307, 1980, <https://doi.org/10.46743/1082-7307/2020.1460>.

⁷Britannica, The Editors of Encyclopaedia. "Mohamed Siad Barre". Encyclopedia Britannica, 5 Dec. 2023, <https://www.britannica.com/biography/Mohamed-Siad-Barre>.

⁸ President Reagan Meeting with President Siad Barre of Somalia. Oval Office on March 11, 1982". *YouTube*.

⁹ Metz, Helen C. ed. "Siad Barre and Scientific Socialism", *Somalia: A Country Study*, Washington, D.C.1992: Library of Congress.

¹⁰ *The Ethiopian Revolution: War in the Horn of Africa*. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press. ISBN 978-0-300-14163-4.

¹¹ UNDP, *Human Development Report 2001-Somalia*, (New York: 2001), p. 42

for the civil war.¹² With the genocide rose the Somali National Movement (SNM) which was a resistance group that started in the North. They fought against Barre's regime and overthrew him in 1991 and declared the northern part of Somalia (Somaliland) separate from the rest of Somalia.¹³

In between the establishment of the transitional government and the civil war, the Somalis in the south adopted Islamic governance in Somalia which can be attributed to the growing prominence of religious symbols and titles post-civil war era, as people turned to religion for solace during challenging times, trusting religious leaders was due to Islam's condemnation of unjust activities.¹⁴ Another factor justifying the significance of religion as a turning point might have been Siad Barre's socialist regime, which lacked an Islamic foundation, may have compelled the Somali people to turn to more Islamic governance alternatives. They had experienced the failures of a regime that did not align with their beliefs, as exemplified by the historic speech in which Barre declared, "Our Socialism is not Islamic, is not African, it is Marxism-Leninism."¹⁵ The Sharia court system was then developed as an alternative to the warlords and garnered popularity. Moreover, the courts received more support from the public because of their defense against the transitional federal government in Somalia, given the Hawiye's absence from power and suspicions about ties to Ethiopia, further elevated their standing. However, the Islamic Militant groups such as the Al-Itihaad, Al-Islamiya (AIAI), the group to which Al-Shabaab's roots are traced back to, presented themselves as part of the court system, gradually gained support and influence before breaking away and establishing

¹² Ibid

¹³Bulhan, Hussein. "Why Somalis Flee A Review of the Gersony Report." *Somali Relief and Rehabilitation*.

¹⁴Hansen, Stig J. *Al-Shabaab in Somalia: The History and Ideology of a Militant Islamist Group*. Oxford University Press, 2016.

¹⁵Abdullahi, Abdurahman M. *The Islamic Movement in Somalia: A Historical Evolution with a Case Study of Islah Movement (1950-2000)*. 2011. Institute of Islamic Studies, McGill University, PhD in the Modern History of Islam. p. 175

themselves as a separate entity. Over time, Al-Shabaab asserted dominance over the transitional government, courts, and other militant groups, ultimately seizing control of Mogadishu (the capital city of Somalia) and other major cities like Kismayo in 2011¹⁶

Furthermore, Al-Shabaab's emergence can be seen as a result of global influences intersecting with local conditions, with the organization's official founders, including veterans from the Afghan-Russian war of 1979-89 played significant roles in its establishment. For example, Al-Qaeda played a crucial role in disseminating their ideas. Particularly, other groups in the region, including Sudan's Hassan Turabi and his "African Pan-Islamic" vision, indirectly influenced the emergence of Al-Shabaab by providing both ideological and technical support to a newly established Al-Shabaab.¹⁷ One of the main developments that these international actors helped with Al-Shabaab was its ideological formation, particularly focusing on its evolution from nationalist Islamism to transnational Islamism. Poor foreign interventions, including the Ethiopian invasion of Somalia, gave the chance for Al-Shabaab to recruit local youth with nationalistic and clanist motivations due to hostility towards the Ethiopian intervention. This highlights the group's strategy of blending nationalist Islamism and transnational Islamism to garner support from local power holders and international entities like Al-Qaeda. In addition, this ideological blend became more visible after the departure of Ethiopia in 2006 when Al-Shabaab adapted and shifted their focus to transnational Islamism and leveraged global issues to justify its existence. They also used this same idea to transcend clan differences by promoting the idea of Islam uniting beyond clan differences.

¹⁶"Somalia Situation Update: October 2023 | Al-Shabaab Strikes Back at Local Administrators." *ACLEDA*, 20 Oct. 2023, acleddata.com/2023/10/20/somalia-situation-update-october-2023-al-shabaab-strikes-back-at-local-administrators/.

¹⁷Hansen, Stig J. *Al-Shabaab in Somalia: The History and Ideology of a Militant Islamist Group*. Oxford University Press, 2016.

History of the Somaliland Region

Before colonization, Somalia did not exist as a state; "Although the Somalis traditionally had a strong sense of cultural and linguistic unity, they did not form a single political unit. They were a nation, not a state."¹⁸ However, beginning in 1839, Britain's interest in the region due to its strategic location near the Gulf of Aden led to the colonization of northern Somalia (Somaliland) by Britain and the southern region by Italy.¹⁹ Somaliland, a British protectorate, gained independence on June 26, 1960, followed shortly by Somalia's independence from Italy on July 1, 1960. In June 1961, Somaliland initiated discussions with Somalia aiming to unify the Somali people under one government.²⁰ Despite this initiative, only Somalia and Somaliland joined together; the NFD in Kenya, and the Ogaden region in Ethiopia, were part of other countries and Djibouti declined the offer.

The unification of the two states "faced challenges early on, with many in Somaliland rejecting the centralization of power in the country's south (Mogadishu)."²¹ While the alliance initially held promise for the Pan-Somali dream, these benefits were overshadowed by mounting difficulties, following Siyad Barre's forceful ascension to power in 1969 after the assassination of the civilian-elected president, Abdurashid Ali Sharmarke.²² Barre's regime, marked by the formation of the Supreme Revolutionary Council (SRC) and his assumption of the Chairmanship and Presidency, intensified concerns among Northern Somalis who sought a fair share of political power due to their minority status.²³ The inequalities in power persisted and intensified

¹⁸Lewis, Ioan M. "Understanding Somalia and Somaliland." *Saxafi Media*, 15 Sept. 2022, saxafimedia.com/understanding-somalia-somaliland-culture-society/#_Toc114076488.

¹⁹Ibid

²⁰Ibid

²¹Klobucista, Claire . "Somaliland: The Horn of Africa's Breakaway State." *Council on Foreign Relations*, 1 Feb. 2018, www.cfr.org/background/somaliland-horn-africas-breakaway-state.

²²Bulhan, Hussein. "Why Somalis Flee A Review of the Gersony Report." *Somali Relief and Rehabilitation*.

²³Ibid

from there on, whatever little resources existed were concentrated in the South, and the industrial sector has been markedly concentrated in the capital, Mogadishu, as have major health services and institutions of higher learning.²⁴ Another reason the unity was becoming less appealing to the Somalis in the North was the influx of refugees from Ethiopia, resulting from the Somalia-Ethiopia conflict and the absence of solidified borders. The refugees consisting of Oromo and other tribes resided in camps in Hargeisa, Berbera, and Borama²⁵ were received with compassion and generosity at first, however, resentment built up as competition over limited resources and services intensified. In addition, the regime used the refugees, as recruitment into harsh measures to persecute and humiliate the Isaaq²⁶. To put it succinctly, these grievances culminated in the establishment of the Somali National Movement (SNM) in 1981, a rebel faction initially lacking widespread support until 1989-90.²⁷ The SNM overthrew Barre's regime and declared Somaliland, an independent state in 1991.²⁸

Initially, the SNM originated in April 1981 from a collective of Somali diaspora in Saudi Arabia, known as the Somali Islamic Democratic (SID) party, serving as an oppositional political force against the Barre regime. Later in May 1981, the Saudi-based group merged with an Isaaq diaspora group in the United Kingdom to form the Somali National Movement (SNM) in London.²⁹ The London-based founders were more secular and nationalist in their outlook than the Saudi-based group who favored an Islamic separatist-oriented movement.³⁰ Yet, despite

²⁴Ibid

²⁵Gersony, Robert. "WHY SOMALIS FLEE." *Bureau for Refugee Programs Department of State*, 1989, pp. 45-47, <https://cja.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/Gersony-Why-Somalis-Flee-Aug-1989.pdf>.

²⁶Isaaq is a major clan that resides in Somaliland that claims descent to Sheik Ishaq from the Arabian peninsula. They suffered a systematic state-sponsored genocide in the hands of the Somali Democratic Republic for rebelling against Barre's regime.

²⁷Bulhan, Hussein. "Why Somalis Flee A Review of the Gersony Report." *Somali Relief and Rehabilitation*.

²⁸Ali, Fatuma. "The Somali National Movement (SNM): Engineering Self-Determination Of Somaliland." *Saxafi Media*, 21 Apr. 2022, saxafimedia.com/somali-national-movement-engineering-somaliland/.

²⁹ Ibid

³⁰ Ibid

successfully overthrowing the regime and declaring Somaliland's independence, the region faced multiple civil wars during its initial two years of statehood. Primarily driven by disputes over economic assets like ports, airports, and land. Efforts were cautiously made to reopen trade routes and reignite commercial activities within Somaliland, driven by the concern that the boundaries defined by clans might solidify into tangible territorial boundaries. The elders responded swiftly and effectively by developing the habit of peace conferences for cities/towns such as Borama, Hargeisa, Sheikh, Darar Weyne, Burco, Agabar and several more towns.³¹ These peace conferences played a pivotal role in preserving the unity of Somaliland, as various tribes were determined to retain control over their territories, fearing potential land loss in the event of renewed conflict. These discussions used a system, known as Geed Fadhiisi, a Somali tradition, that involves gathering for collective discussions. This tradition, which translates to "sitting under a tree" in English, is also employed when families seek a daughter's hand in marriage or when various clans convene for discussions. This system produced a blend of democracy and traditional Somali governance that continues to rule in Somaliland and served as a shield against internal threats to Somaliland's stability.

Moreover, the narrative of the SNM is intriguing because one might anticipate their continued presence in Somaliland's political landscape after liberating the country from the regime. However, the movement's leaders stepped down and handed over power to a new civil administration. Also, "most of the rank and field fighters demobilized themselves spontaneously and returned to civil life and the SNM opted for the natural *xeer* (customary law)."³² In a bottom-up approach, customary law in Somaliland resolved issues by clan consensus during

³¹Renders, Marleen. *Consider Somaliland State-Building with Traditional Readers and Institutions*. vol. 26, Brill, 2012.

³²Ali, Fatuma. "The Somali National Movement (SNM): Engineering Self-Determination Of Somaliland." *Saxafi Media*, 21 Apr. 2022, saxafimedia.com/somali-national-movement-engineering-somaliland/.

conferences mediated by elders, supported by various sectors including businessmen, religious figures, civil society, and scholars in Somaliland and abroad.³³ In this context, the SNM's departure was opportune as they had effectively concluded their fight, providing an opportunity for broader community conflict resolution. The Somali National Movement is a unique example of how a movement can transform itself from political opposition to a rebel group and then to a government.

While Somaliland strived to mend its relations within the region, tensions persisted in Somaliland-Somalia relations following Somaliland's declaration of independence, as Somalia continued to reject and refuse acknowledgment of Somaliland's sovereignty. The ongoing standoff between the two states led to discussions on reconciliation, yet these talks have yielded limited benefits. While discussions between Somalia and Somaliland failed to make headway on sovereignty matters, the resumption of dialogue offers an opportunity to enhance collaboration on crucial technical aspects such as international aid, airspace management, and security cooperation.³⁴ It is evident from the discussions that Somaliland demonstrates no interest in reunification with Somalia but remains open to dialogue on issues like border disputes and technical security matters. Somaliland's reaction to Ugandan President Museveni's offer to mediate reunification talks earlier this year was a clear example: "The Somaliland Government affirms that any dialogue that transpires between Somaliland and Somalia will not discuss unification, but rather how the two previously united countries can move forward separately,"³⁵

The most notable interaction between Somalia and Somaliland occurred when Somalia mediated

³³ Ibid

³⁴"Somalia-Somaliland: A Halting Embrace of Dialogue." *Crisis Group*, 6 Aug. 2020, www.crisisgroup.org/africa/horn-africa/somalia/somalia-somaliland-halting-embrace-dialogue.

³⁵"Somaliland Rejects Talk of Unification with Somalia After Museveni Comment." *AL JAZEERA AND NEWS AGENCIES*, 25 Sep. 2023.

between Puntland³⁶ and Somaliland during the 2018 border conflict at the battle of Tukaraq, where Puntland and Somaliland clashed over contested territory. Intergovernmental Authority on Development and United Nations Assistance Mission in Somalia mediated a ceasefire agreement between Somaliland and Puntland, but by the end of the year neither party publicly supported the terms of the agreement.³⁷ The lack of progress in these discussions stems from mutual distrust between the two states and the absence of an unbiased mediator. Each mediator involved in these talks is diplomatically aligned with either Somalia or Somaliland, inadvertently causing resentment from the opposing side.

Somaliland continues to garner international support, yet its sovereignty remains unacknowledged. Discussions often see the West deferring to African nations, who, in turn, defer to Somalia, staunchly opposing Somaliland's quest for sovereignty. However, recent developments mark significant progress. The investment of \$442 million by a Dubai-based port operator, the largest in Somaliland's history, is anticipated to be transformative for its economy.³⁸ This move grants the United Arab Emirates (UAE) an alternative regional foothold, particularly through the Berbera port, following Djibouti's 2018 seizure of the DP World facility amid long-standing disputes. Mogadishu's government, allied with Turkey and Qatar (rivals to the UAE), has witnessed other nations establishing a presence in Somaliland, including the UAE sending a permanent diplomat in March 2021.³⁹ Kenya announced plans for a consulate in the

³⁶ Puntland is a Federal member state in Northeastern Somalia, it became an autonomous region from Somalia in 1998. The region seeks the unity of Somalis and is not trying to obtain international recognition as a separate nation like Somaliland.

³⁷"Somalia: Somaliland Forces Take Control of Tukaraq." *GaroweOnline*, 1 Aug. 2018, www.garoweonline.com/en/news/puntland/somalia-somaliland-forces-take-control-of-tukaraq.

³⁸"Somaliland, an Unrecognised State, Is Winning Friends Abroad." *The Economist*, 8 May 2021, www.economist.com/middle-east-and-africa/2021/05/06/somaliland-an-unrecognised-state-is-winning-friends-abroad.

³⁹ Ibid

capital, while Taiwan opened its East Africa office in Hargeisa, offering aid despite Chinese opposition due to Somaliland's refusal to support the "one China" principle.⁴⁰

Despite the accomplishments in international advancements, Somaliland faces internal challenges. For example, Somaliland's 2001 constitution aimed to diminish clan influence in politics by restricting political parties to a maximum of three, fostering coalition building.⁴¹ However, despite this framework, most voters consistently align their votes along clan lines. This system perpetuates stagnation, distributing employment and contracts based on clan affiliation rather than merit. Institutions designed for government oversight are feeble and judges often yield to the executive and seldom pursue corruption charges. Whereas the parliament also functions more as a formality.⁴² May 31st, 2021 marks Somaliland's first parliamentary elections in 16 years. Moreover, atop these challenges, Somaliland grapples with severe unemployment. Jama Musse Jama, Hargeisa Cultural Centre director, highlighted that 70% of the population is under 30 years old. He emphasizes that beyond peace, 'these youngsters demand employment and opportunities. Currently, an estimated 75% of them are unemployed'.⁴³ After 32 years of rebuilding, Somaliland has succeeded in establishing a functioning government without international recognition. Yet, it still has a significant journey ahead to demonstrate to its people the breadth of benefits it can offer beyond peace and security.

Al-Shabaab Attacks and Activities in Somaliland

Currently, Al-Shabaab shows minimal interest in Somaliland due to its geographical distance, requiring passage through Puntland or Ethiopia, both of which strongly oppose the group's activities. Moreover, Somaliland's economy, less prosperous compared to Somalia, offers

⁴⁰ Ibid

⁴¹ Ibid

⁴² Ibid

⁴³ Ibid

fewer benefits to Al-Shabaab. However, Al-Shabaab has attempted and achieved some successful operations in Somaliland. The last major attack occurred in 2008 when Al-Shabaab targeted the presidential palace, the Ethiopian consulate, and UNDP offices in Hargeisa, Somaliland's capital, resulting in 25 casualties within seven minutes.⁴⁴ Guards outside Somaliland's presidential palace opened fire on the attackers blocking them from entering the compound. One car managed to get into the heavily fortified UNDP office complex before the explosives were detonated. Eyewitnesses at the UNDP office said the attackers parked the car next to one of the buildings, which suffered the worst damage and heaviest casualties. Despite Al-Shabaab not claiming responsibility for the attacks, US intelligence attributed them to the group, citing Ethiopia as a primary target.⁴⁵

Another earlier Al-Shabaab attack in Somaliland occurred in October 2003 when two British teachers were fatally shot by gunmen. The assailants targeted the teachers through the window of their flat within a school compound in Sheikh. The attack was motivated by religious reasons, as the boarding school, established during British colonial rule, had faced severe damage during the 1989 civil war. Following the incident, the Austrian aid agency SOS Children's intervened.⁴⁶ Additionally, an Italian aid worker was killed two weeks before the teachers' attack in another direct Al-Shabaab attack. President Riyaleh Kahin stated that these assaults aimed to destabilize the republic, coercing participation in the disintegrating peace talks intended to resolve Somalia's protracted civil war.⁴⁷ Al-Shabaab seemed to oppose foreign involvement, making aid workers their targets, possibly under the Islamist movement's agenda,

⁴⁴Horton, Michael. "How Somaliland Combats Al-Shabaab." *Combating Terrorism Center*, 1 Nov. 2019, ctc.westpoint.edu/somaliland-combats-al-shabaab/.

⁴⁵"Deadly Car Bombs Hit Somaliland." *BBC News | Africa*, 29 Oct. 2008, news.bbc.co.uk/2/hi/africa/7696986.stm.

⁴⁶Branigan, Tania, and Andrew Meldrum. "British Teachers Shot Dead at Somaliland School." *The Guardian*, 22 Oct. 2003, www.theguardian.com/world/2003/oct/22/schools.schoolsworldwide.

⁴⁷ Ibid

rejecting non-Muslims in Somali territory. While there's no evidence of Somalilanders joining Al-Shabaab, Somaliland's geographic location is exploited as a route to transport recruits from elsewhere to Somalia.⁴⁸ Foreigners, having no connections in Somalia, are sometimes directed to Somaliland first to reduce the risk of detection by both the Somali government and their home countries, before proceeding to Somalia by car or other means. Although the distinction between Somalia and Somaliland might lack clarity for numerous international countries, neighboring nations like Ethiopia and Djibouti recognize Somaliland as distinct from Somalia due to their greater familiarity with the realities on the ground.

Factors Contributing to Al-Shabaab's Absence in Somaliland; Governance

Somaliland's political structure consists of the president who is the head of the state and is elected on a national level and a legislature. The president is elected by the people for a five-year term. The Parliament has two chambers. The House of Representatives has 82 members, elected for a five-year term. The House of Elders has 82 members, representing traditional leaders. Somaliland has a multi-party system, with parties in which no one party often has a chance of gaining power alone, and parties must work with each other to form coalition governments.⁴⁹ On an investigation, done by the Freedom House's political rights and civil liberty rankings, "Somaliland is ranked as 'partly free' (with a score of 42/100) whereas, neighboring countries such as Ethiopia (22), Djibouti (24) and Somalia (7) all rank as 'unfree', and the same is true for Uganda (34), Rwanda (21), Burundi (14), Egypt (18), Sudan (17), South Sudan (2) and Eritrea (2) in the next regional ring. Only Kenya (48) to the south also enjoys

⁴⁸Hansen, Stig J. *Al-Shabaab in Somalia: The History and Ideology of a Militant Islamist Group*. Oxford University Press, 2016.

⁴⁹MGoth. "Briefing Piper Somaliland Voter Cards Distribution." *Somaliland Press*, 3 Aug. 2017, www.somalilandpress.com/briefing-paper-somaliland-voter-cards-distribution/.

‘partly free’ status.”⁵⁰ Although this investigation represents a domestically grown expression of democracy rather than one imposed, it signifies unity and favor towards democratic governance. This stands in stark contrast to what Al-Shabaab offers any society. A communal understanding, while potentially lacking the required implementation, effectively deters Al-Shabaab as its ideologies struggle to flourish in an environment fostered by unity.

The Somaliland government's essential function involves domestic revenue collection, including duties on import/export goods at Berbera port and a 5% income tax on business sales. For instance, "duties at the Berbera port generate an estimated 85% of government revenue."⁵¹ With limited foreign aid, much of Somaliland's infrastructure and services rely on taxes. These taxes are primarily collected by the Ministry of Finance in collaboration with the Central Bank.⁵² The tax system involves duty and income taxes on business sales, import/export goods, consumption of goods/services (equivalent to VAT), employee salaries (PAYE), and property investments.⁵³ The Ministry officials visit businesses to collect taxes, which are self-assessed and declaratory, requiring minimal record-keeping other than sales records.⁵⁴ Additionally, there are other levies and user charges by specific government ministries and agencies for services and permits. However, there appears to be limited coordination among authorities regarding charges. The efficiency of tax administration and collection costs remains unclear. The majority of businesses fall within the informal sector, resulting in a small and unreliable tax base.⁵⁵ Many of

⁵⁰Mills, Greg, et al. "Somaliland: The Power of Democracy." *RUSI*, 4 June. 2021, www.rusi.org/explore-our-research/publications/commentary/somaliland-power-democracy.

⁵¹ <https://www.govsomaliland.org/articles/government-1>

⁵²Ahmed, Mohammed D. "Somaliland: Taxation System." *SomalilandSun*, 8 Jan. 2016, somalilandsun.com/somaliland-taxation-system/.

⁵³ Tellander, Ebba, and Mohamed A. Hassan. "Accountability in the Taxation System in Somaliland." *The Peace Research Institute Oslo*, 24 Jan. 2016, css.ethz.ch/content/dam/ethz/special-interest/gess/cis/center-for-securities-studies/resources/docs/PRIO-Accountability%20in%20the%20Taxation%20System%20in%20Somaliland.pdf.

⁵⁴ Ibid

⁵⁵ Ibid

these businesses are not part of the tax net, while compliance costs for those included are high. Inadequate record-keeping leads to challenges in assessing tax liabilities, fostering unfair competition among enterprises and contributing to taxpayer non-compliance.⁵⁶ The absence of a unified revenue collection structure has shifted focus from general taxes to specific taxes targeting particular activities, easier and cheaper to administer. Although these taxes generate a significant portion of the income for the Somaliland government, the government must focus not only on efficient extraction from the port but also on smaller businesses. This approach is essential to prevent exploitation by other entities.

Counterterrorism Efforts in Resisting Al-Shabaab

The Somaliland government has the capacity to thwart Al-Shabaab's attempts to insert itself and its operatives into communities where it could then establish its shadow government. It achieves this through a virtuous circle that starts with locally derived governance that connects to the broader governance. For example, in the Somali culture, each clan has its chiefs and Suldans, and each sub-clan and family has its sub-chief or elder. However, the nation-state has to overpower all these power structures while at the same time not taking their relevance away which consequently causes decentralization of the power of the government back into the local communities. In addition, it ensures the flow of information and a system of trust between the higher level governance and the locals. Furthermore, “this system then provides the critical Human Intelligence (HUMINT) that allows the government to combat militancy. This capacity to combat militancy contributes to the security and governance that yields the broad support that allows the circle to perpetuate itself.”⁵⁷

⁵⁶ Ibid

⁵⁷Horton, Michael. "How Somaliland Combats Al-Shabaab." *Combating Terrorism Center*, 1 Nov. 2019, ctc.westpoint.edu/somaliland-combats-al-shabaab/.

This system could be associated with British colonialism, particularly as Somaliland was a British protectorate. The British rule in Somaliland was characterized by limited involvement and an absence of settlers, often referred to as Britain's 'Cinderella of empire'.⁵⁸ It is arguable that colonial impact shaped governance, evident in the reliance on clan chiefs to govern,⁵⁹ a tradition of mixing foreign administration with local traditions. This decentralized power structure has notably contributed to counterterrorism efforts and community policing in Somaliland. Such influences often shape a nation's post-colonial identity and patriotism.

Ironically, Al-Shabaab employs a similar decentralization of power. For instance, when Al-Shabaab was on the brink of collapse after defeating the federal Transitional Government and Ethiopian forces withdrew, they gained control over vast territories, resulting in a rise of militias. To prevent fragmentation, Al-Shabaab tactfully appointed clan leaders to low-level command positions, giving them a semblance of influence within the organization.⁶⁰ This strategic move aimed to retain control over clans and prevent their disintegration from Al-Shabaab's influence. It is intriguing to note the parallels: while Somaliland utilizes decentralization to involve clan elders in governance, Al-Shabaab employs it to prevent militias from turning against them. Both entities employ similar systems to prevent fragmentation and maintain control.

Somaliland has not only employed ideological, and local governance tactics in counterterrorism but has also increased its military responses to threats, particularly following the 2008 attack on the Parliament, prompting the government of Somaliland, with some assistance from the United Nations and the United Kingdom, to create the Special Protection

⁵⁸Lewis, Ioan M. "Understanding Somalia and Somaliland." *Saxafi Media*, 15 Sept. 2022, saxafimedia.com/understanding-somalia-somaliland-culture-society/#_Toc114076488.

⁵⁹"Italian Vs. British Colonialism Helps Explain Somalia Vs. Somaliland Difference." *History News Network*, 7 Mar. 2007, historynewsnetwork.org/article/36869.

⁶⁰Hansen, Stig J. *Al-Shabaab in Somalia: The History and Ideology of a Militant Islamist Group*. Oxford University Press, 2016.

Unit (SPU), a police force tasked with protecting foreign organizations in its territory and those who work for them. At the same time, Somaliland began to build up its intelligence-gathering capabilities in response to the increased threats from militant groups.⁶¹ This is an example of a system and law enforcement put in place to avoid incidents like the killing of aid workers in 2003 and the attacks on the presidential palace, the Ethiopian consulate, and UNDP offices in Hargeisa in 2008. Around the same time the Rapid Reaction Unit (RRU), a Somaliland paramilitary counter-terror squad was established in 2012.⁶² These are both military-related measures that the Somaliland government took to prevent threats from terrorists like Al-Shabaab.

Some of the other initiatives that Somaliland took were strengthening local governance, counterterrorism, and community-driven intelligence initiatives. This was done by increasing district governance and building ties between the communities, police, and military.⁶³ The system of the Suldaan or chiefs existed prior to the Al-Shabaab attacks but they were not well funded and there was not a strong connection between the chief elders in local communities and the police. Therefore, community leaders gained access to officials at the national level if they felt they had not received an adequate response from district- and regional-level authorities. This also put pressure on the government to respond faster. Since Somaliland does not have an air force, drones, or even a budget to supply its soldiers with weapons⁶⁴ It relies on informal intelligence-gathering networks that are nested within local communities. Formal networks led by officers from the National Intelligence Service (NIS), army, and police exist alongside and in

⁶¹Horton, Michael. "How Somaliland Combats Al-Shabaab." *Combating Terrorism Center*, 1 Nov. 2019, ctc.westpoint.edu/somaliland-combats-al-shabaab/.

⁶²Bryant, Ben. "UK Accused of Training and Supporting Deadly Somaliland Counter-Terrorism Unit." *Vice News*, 10 Dec. 2014, www.vice.com/en/article/ev7wz7/uk-accused-of-training-and-supporting-deadly-somaliland-counter-terrorism-unit.

⁶³Horton, Michael. "How Somaliland Combats Al-Shabaab." *Combating Terrorism Center*, 1 Nov. 2019, ctc.westpoint.edu/somaliland-combats-al-shabaab/.

⁶⁴ Ibid

conjunction with the informal networks that act as early detection systems.⁶⁵ The key to Somaliland's combat against terrorism is the hybrid of traditional power structures and authority with representative democracy that supports the government in diffusing and mitigating conflict while keeping the government close to the people it governs. This shows the creativity of the Somali governance and the will for counterterrorism efforts despite their lack of tools that might be deemed essential to the job.

Sociocultural Factors in Combating Al-Shabaab

In addition to relying on informal intelligence networks embedded within local communities Somaliland concurrently reinforced its counterterrorism strategies through the establishment of formal networks led by the National Intelligence Service (NIS), army, and police. Hence, the role of individuals within the intelligence-gathering system becomes indispensable, since it compensates for technical shortcomings in the system. Human Intelligence stands as the cornerstone of Somaliland's counter-terrorism strategy.⁶⁶ Accurate and timely human intelligence that allows for quick responses to threats stemming from close informal and formal ties between Somaliland's military and intelligence service and those communities most vulnerable to Al-Shabaab. Additionally, the United Kingdom actively supports Somaliland's counterterrorism efforts through the funding and training of the Rapid Response Unit (RRU). This assistance encompasses a range of provisions, such as security equipment, vehicles, a UK-constructed headquarters, and a pretrial detention facility, all designated as part of the UK's counter-terrorism program.⁶⁷ While foreign troops training local

⁶⁵ Ibid

⁶⁶Horton, Michael. "How Somaliland Combats Al-Shabaab." *Combating Terrorism Center*, 1 Nov. 2019, ctc.westpoint.edu/somaliland-combats-al-shabaab/.

⁶⁷Bryant, Ben. "UK Accused of Training and Supporting Deadly Somaliland Counter-Terrorism Unit." *Vice News*, 10 Dec. 2014, www.vice.com/en/article/ev7wz7/uk-accused-of-training-and-supporting-deadly-somaliland-counter-terrorism-unit.

military in counterterrorism have proven beneficial in Somaliland, there are inherent limitations and risks. British officials view Al-Shabaab as a distant problem and may train troops with that mindset, disregarding the RRUs' proximity to Al-Shabaab physically, culturally, and in other various life aspects. Moreover, the residual impact of colonial history remains palpable, manifesting in nuanced ways. The RRU, which is funded and trained by a former colonizing empire, faces public scrutiny from Somaliland for excessive force and mistreatment of civilians and suspects.⁶⁸ Despite aiming for counterterrorism, such actions inadvertently generate negative perceptions among locals. Beyond these external influences, Somaliland's distinct cultural practices and differences persist, shaping its societal fabric and identity.

Although the majority of Somalis share similar cultural and social dynamics, subtle differences may contribute to the absence of Al-Shabaab in certain regions. Notably, ethnic distinctions play a role, with the Isaaq clan forming the majority in Somaliland alongside other clans, while the Hawiye clan is prevalent in Somalia along with various other clans. While there are minor variations in cultural practices, such as nuances in daily traditions, the overarching language spoken is Somali. In the southern regions near the Juba and Shabelle rivers, Agro-Pastoralist communities thrive due to the availability of water resources, while the northern areas predominantly practice pastoralism due to the semi-arid climate that limits agriculture.⁶⁹ Despite the commonality of the Somali language, distinct dialects and accents exist among different regions. This divergence is noticeable even within Somaliland, where variations in accents between regions like Burco and Gabiley are evident through the usage of different words and expressions. Similar dialect differences are also found in Somalia, such as the Banaadir,

⁶⁸Ibid

⁶⁹Lewis, Ioan M. "Understanding Somalia and Somaliland." *Saxafi Media*, 15 Sept. 2022, saxafimedia.com/understanding-somalia-somaliland-culture-society/#_Toc114076488.

Ashraaf, May, and Digil dialects.⁷⁰ These subtle variations might contribute to the differentiation between Somaliland and Somalia, potentially impacting human intelligence as accents play a noticeable role in identifying individuals.

The core of Somaliland nationalism revolves around the narrative of historical marginalization in the north and the repression endured under the former military regime in Mogadishu. Emphasizing their democratic values in stark contrast to ongoing instability in Somalia,⁷¹ Somalilanders unite over shared grievances from the past regime, memorializing these struggles in city landmarks. For instance, the MiG Jet, A Russian Fighter jet, an emblem of the oppressive Bare regime and used during the Isaaq genocide, stands today as a monument in Hargeisa.⁷² These elements significantly contribute to the collective national identity of Somalilanders, fostering unity and resistance against ideologies like Al-Shabaab that have not partaken in this shared historical struggle. This cohesion diminishes the likelihood of Al-Shabaab finding sanctuary within the community.

Security And Border Control

Ideologically, Somaliland remains relatively insulated from Al-Shabaab; however, there are security vulnerabilities along its borders, particularly in disputed areas bordering Puntland. Puntland, established as an autonomous region from Somalia in 1998, lays claim to Lasanod due to clan kinship ties in the region. Somaliland gained control of Lasanod in 2007, designating it as the capital of the Sool region, and has since maintained authority over the area.⁷³ Somaliland's

⁷⁰"Somali Dialects/Accent Map. Which One Do You Speak?" *The Somali Spot*, 18 Sept. 2020, <https://www.somalispot.com/threads/somali-dialects-accent-map-which-one-do-you-speak.96445/>.

⁷¹Chonka, Peter, and Sally Healy. "Self-determination and a Shattered Star: Statehood and National Identity in the Somali Horn of Africa." *Wiley Online Library*, 22 Dec. 2020, onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1111/nana.12646.

⁷²Dunnell, Tony. "Hargeisa War Memorial." *AtlasObscura*, 1 Apr. 2022, www.atlasobscura.com/places/hargeisa-war-memorial.

⁷³Hoehne, Markus V. "Puntland and Somaliland Clashing in Northern Somalia: Who Cuts the Gordian Knot?" *Web Archive*, 7 Nov. 2007, web.archive.org/web/20071117043205/http://hornofafrica.ssrc.org/Hoehne/printable.htm.

capture of Lasanod was grounded in territorial claims dating back to the British colonial era. The dispute over Lasanod was reignited earlier in 2023, notably involving the SSC-Khaatumo State (Sool, Sanaag, Cayn regions), an interim administration primarily representing the Dhulbahante clan. This group seeks autonomy both from Puntland and Somaliland, claiming Lasanod and other territories in Somaliland as their own due to Dhulbahante's presence in those regions.⁷⁴ Somaliland has allocated 2% of its budget for the development of Sool and neighboring Sanaag regions and previously implemented a power-sharing agreement recognizing the Dhulbahante's minority status.⁷⁵ The current President, Muse Bihi, declined to uphold this agreement. Consequently, the Lasanod community faced security concerns including the assassinations of their officials, feeling unprotected by the Somaliland government.⁷⁶ This led the SSC-Khaatumo to intervene, leveraging those grievances to sway the people of Lasanod against the Somaliland government. Although the SSC-Khaatumo group does not pose a major threat to Somaliland and has declared a ceasefire regarding the conflict over Lasanod.⁷⁷ Moreover, Puntland and Somalia hold trade interests, creating challenges for the survival of the Khaatumo group within an environment marked by the competition for resources between two significant autonomous entities, Somaliland and Puntland.⁷⁸ Sustainable peace along this border is imperative to prevent future conflicts or grievances.

Despite intermittent clashes between Puntland and Somaliland, Puntland undeniably influences the geographical landscape, creating obstacles that impede Al-Shabaab's access to

⁷⁴"Time for Somaliland and the Dhulbahante to Talk." *International Crisis Group*, 19 May 2023, www.crisisgroup.org/africa/horn-africa/somaliland/time-somaliland-and-dhulbahante-talk.

⁷⁵ Ibid

⁷⁶ Ibid

⁷⁷"SSC-Khaatumo Declares Cessation of Conflict in Sool, Sanag, and Cayn Areas." *Hiiraan*, 29 Aug. 2023,

hiiraan.com/news4/2023/Aug/192813/ssc_khatumo_declares_cessation_of_conflict_in_sool_sanag_and_cayn_areas.aspx.

⁷⁸ Ibid

Somaliland. For instance, Puntland unintentionally acts as a buffer state for Somaliland as the defector group from Al-Shabaab, the Islamic State in Somalia Province (ISSP), operates in Puntland, effectively hindering Al-Shabaab's presence in that region. Any attempt by Al-Shabaab to reach Somaliland would require passage through Puntland, where ISSP's presence restricts Al-Shabaab's movements. The ISSP pledged allegiance to ISIS in October 2015 and gained recognition as an official province in 2018.⁷⁹ These regional terrorist groups differ in their goals because Al-Qaeda aims to establish Islamic governments by overthrowing corrupt regimes in the Middle East, considering the United States as the main obstacle. Whereas, 'ISSP adheres to ISIS's strict interpretation of Islamic law and aims to extend ISIS's self-proclaimed caliphate in Africa'.⁸⁰

Moreover, Mogadishu, situated farther south in Somalia, presents a considerable distance, posing a challenge to the freedom of movement. Notably, a difference stemming from colonial regimes between Somaliland and Somalia is Somalia's cosmopolitan nature, which facilitated Al-Shabaab's easy establishment and economic laundering.⁸¹ Conversely, Somaliland's less developed economic status might deter Al-Shabaab, as there is limited profitability potential.

Future Prospects

Future challenges for Somaliland may involve a potential clash with the SSC group due to the absence of a formal peace treaty. Additionally, Puntland's control of the Bosaso port presents the risk of the SSC-Khaatumo group exploiting arms trafficking, which could be used against the aspirations of territories they claim.⁸² The group's conflict, rooted primarily in

⁷⁹Foreign Terrorist Organization; ISIS Somalia." *National Counterterrorism Center* | FTOs, Sep. 2022, https://www.dni.gov/nctc/ftos/isis_somalia_fto.html.

⁸⁰ Ibid

⁸¹Lewis, Ioan M. "Understanding Somalia and Somaliland." *Saxafi Media*, 15 Sept. 2022, saxafimedia.com/understanding-somalia-somaliland-culture-society/#_Toc114076488.

⁸²O'Connell, David. "Disrupting Arms Trafficking in Somali Waters." *UNODC East African News and Stores*, 31 May 2023, www.unodc.org/easternafrika/en/Stories/disrupting-arms-trafficking-in-somali-waters-.html.

kinship, renders them vulnerable to potential influence by Al-Shabaab, who, currently being pushed southward and experiencing significant losses in Somalia, might seek refuge with the SSC group until their recovery. However, the prevention of these scenarios largely relies on the relationship between Puntland and Somaliland, as well as the ISSP's fight against Al-Shabaab, making such outcomes less likely. Moreover, this issue extends beyond a mere border dispute between Somaliland and Puntland, while that may dominate surface-level news, it involves international powerhouses. Although there exists no concrete evidence linking Beijing directly to the Lasanod conflict, numerous circumstantial factors warrant attention. Before the outbreak of the unrest, a Somali individual known as 'Ruush' ('The Russian'), formerly associated with Hess Oil in the region, was observed engaging with the Chinese ambassador in Mogadishu.⁸³ Concurrently, Abdullahi Haji Omar 'Amey,' the former vice president of Puntland, who has held the position of Somali ambassador in Ethiopia since 2019, had meetings with his Chinese counterpart. In a public speech, Amey openly acknowledged orchestrating the Las Anod violence, a plan he purportedly formulated for four months.

Initially, China aimed to establish relations with Somaliland but faced rejection when Somaliland chose to align itself with Taiwan in February 2020. Despite previous disregard by China, their ambassador to Somalia made a direct appeal to Somaliland's President, Muse Bihi, to reverse this decision, which was met with refusal.⁸⁴ Also, Somaliland's discovery of potentially lucrative oil reserves increased the region's strategic importance. China, displeased with Somaliland's leaning towards the West and the strengthening of ties with Taiwan, intensified its efforts to assert influence in Somalia.⁸⁵ China's reaction included an increase in efforts to

⁸³Phillips, Michael M. "China Fumes Over Somaliland's Warm Ties With Taiwan Few African Regions Have the Nerve to Say No to China. Independence-minded Somaliland Is One." *The Wall Street Journal*, 11 Aug. 2022, www.wsj.com/articles/china-fumes-as-somaliland-refuses-to-unfriend-taiwan-11660213603.

⁸⁴Ibid

⁸⁵Ibid

bolster its influence in Somalia while potentially sidelining Somaliland. This move coincided with the State Department's initiative to direct significant financial aid through President Hassan Sheikh Mohamud's government in Mogadishu, signaling a form of competition for influence and control in the region between China and the West.

I strongly advise Somaliland to maintain close ties with allies such as Taiwan and foster support and trust in these relationships, as they embody genuine partnerships. However, it is crucial to extend diplomatic support rather than being drawn into the power struggles characteristic of superpowers vying for influence. This perpetual cycle underscores the need for Somaliland not to become a casualty of such conflicts. Taiwan enjoys support from other nations, notably the United States. It is unnecessary for Somaliland to limit opportunities or connections with other countries solely because of a successful diplomatic alliance with one. While Somaliland has made significant progress, it remains relatively fragile compared to these global supporters, relying heavily on them. Amidst these dynamics, maintaining focus on the primary goal of attaining recognition is important.

Conclusion

Somaliland's history, from pre-colonization to its declaration of independence after overthrowing Barre's regime, is a tale of struggle, resilience, and adaptation. Despite internal challenges, strides in international relations and economic developments signify progress, but the journey toward recognition, governance reform, and addressing youth unemployment remains pivotal for its future stability and growth. A theme revealed in the state-building processes of Somaliland and the Somali National Movement was prioritizing the state over personal desires. This approach embodies a true form of democracy. Somaliland, as an emerging nation, presents a

revitalized version of democracy, distinct from the traditional model traced back to the 1800s in the US.

Somaliland continues to function as a state and has implemented a robust counterterrorism strategy that combines decentralized governance, community-oriented policing, and military responses. Leveraging traditional power structures alongside representative democracy, it effectively diffuses conflict and maintains close ties between the government and local communities, showcasing resourcefulness in combating terrorism despite limited resources. In addition, the counterterrorism strategy combines formal and informal intelligence networks, emphasizing the indispensability of human intelligence. While external support, like that from the UK, aids in capacity building, the region's distinct cultural diversity, historical narratives, and shared grievances foster a strong national identity that acts as a deterrent against threats posed by groups like Al-Shabaab.

Somaliland's relative insulation from Al-Shabaab is influenced by its geographical dynamics and border disputes, notably with Puntland. While vulnerabilities exist along its borders, the presence of groups like the Islamic State in Somalia Province (ISSP) in Puntland inadvertently acts as a buffer, impeding Al-Shabaab's direct access to Somaliland. The region's historical disputes and economic differences contribute to a complex security landscape, making sustainable peace along its borders crucial for preventing potential conflicts or threats. Al-Shabaab is not present in Somaliland due to several factors, including strong local governance, effective counterterrorism efforts, community engagement, and geographical barriers limiting the group's infiltration into the region. However, the challenges ahead for Somaliland, including potential clashes with the SSC group and risks posed by Puntland's control of Bosaso port, underline the importance of strategic alliances and diplomatic support, notably

with Taiwan. However, Somaliland must navigate international power struggles wisely, focusing on its primary objective of gaining recognition while preserving connections and opportunities with various nations to ensure its stability and progress.

References

- Abdullahi, Abdurahman M. *The Islamic Movement in Somalia: A Historical Evolution with a Case Study of Islah Movement (1950-2000)*. 2011. Institute of Islamic Studies, McGill University, PhD in the Modern History of Islam.
- Ahmed, Mohammed D. "Somaliland: Taxation System." *SomalilandSun*, 8 Jan. 2016, somalilandsun.com/somaliland-taxation-system/.
- Ali, Fatuma. "The Somali National Movement (SNM): Engineering Self-Determination Of Somaliland." *Saxafi Media*, 21 Apr. 2022, saxafimedia.com/somali-national-movement-engineering-somaliland/. Accessed 21 Nov. 2023.
- "Al-Shabaab Whetting Sword near the Border of Ethiopia." *Hiiraan*, 22 Nov. 2023, www.hiiraan.com/news4/2023/sept/192990/al_shabaab_whetting_sword_near_the_border_of_ethiopia.aspx. Accessed 21 Nov. 2023.
- Branigan, Tania , and Andrew Meldrum. "British Teachers Shot Dead at Somaliland School." *The Guardian*, 22 Oct. 2003, www.theguardian.com/world/2003/oct/22/schools.schoolsworldwide. Accessed 23 Nov. 2023.
- Britannica, The Editors of Encyclopaedia. "Mohamed Siad Barre". Encyclopedia Britannica, 5 Dec. 2023, <https://www.britannica.com/biography/Mohamed-Siad-Barre>. Accessed 14 December 2023.
- Bryant, Ben. "UK Accused of Training and Supporting Deadly Somaliland Counter-Terrorism Unit." *Vice News*, 10 Dec. 2014, www.vice.com/en/article/ev7wz7/uk-accused-of-training-and-supporting-deadly-somaliland-counter-terrorism-unit. Accessed 24 Nov. 2023.
- Bulhan, Hussein. "Why Somalis Flee A Review of the Gersony Report." *Somali Relief and Rehabilitation*.
- Chonka, Peter, and Sally Healy. "Self-determination and a Shattered Star: Statehood and National Identity in the Somali Horn of Africa." *Wiley Online Library*, 22 Dec. 2020, onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1111/nana.12646.
- "Deadly Car Bombs Hit Somaliland." *BBC News | Africa*, 29 Oct. 2008, news.bbc.co.uk/2/hi/africa/7696986.stm. Accessed 23 Nov. 2023.
- Dunnell, Tony. "Hargeisa War Memorial." *AtlasObscura*, 1 Apr. 2022, www.atlasobscura.com/places/hargeisa-war-memorial.

- Egoshin, Alex. "Former and Current Unrecognised States in Africa." *Vivid Maps*, vividmaps.com/former-current-unrecognised-states-africa/.
- Foreign Terrorist Organization; Al-Shabaab." *National Counterterrorism Center| FTOs*, Dec. 2021, www.dni.gov/nctc/ftos/al_shabaab_fto.html. Accessed 21 Nov. 2023.
- Foreign Terrorist Organization; ISIS Somalia." *National Counterterrorism Center| FTOs*, Sep. 2022, https://www.dni.gov/nctc/ftos/isis_somalia_fto.html. Accessed 21 Nov. 2023.
- Gersony, Robert. "WHY SOMALIS FLEE." *Bureau for Refugee Programs Department of State*, 1989, pp. 45-47, <https://cja.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/Gersony-Why-Somalis-Flee-Aug-1989.pdf>.
- Lewis, Ioan M. "Understanding Somalia and Somaliland." *Saxafi Media*, 15 Sept. 2022, saxafimedia.com/understanding-somalia-somaliland-culture-society/#_Toc114076488.
- Hansen, Stig J. *Al-Shabaab in Somalia: The History and Ideology of a Militant Islamist Group*. Oxford University Press, 2016.
- Hoehne, Markus V. "Puntland and Somaliland Clashing in Northern Somalia: Who Cuts the Gordian Knot?" *Web Archive*, 7 Nov. 2007, web.archive.org/web/20071117043205/http://hornofafrica.ssrc.org/Hoehne/printable.htm.
- Horton, Michael. "How Somaliland Combats Al-Shabaab." *Combating Terrorism Center*, 1 Nov. 2019, ctc.westpoint.edu/somaliland-combats-al-shabaab/. Accessed 23 Nov. 2023.
- Horton, Michael. "No Foothold for Al-Shabaab in Somaliland." *The Jamestown Foundation*, 14 Aug. 2020, web.archive.org/web/20210212040513/https://jamestown.org/program/no-foothold-for-al-shabaab-in-somaliland/.
- "Italian Vs. British Colonialism Helps Explain Somalia Vs. Somaliland Difference." *History News Network*, 7 Mar. 2007, historynewsnetwork.org/article/36869.
- Klobucista, Claire . "Somaliland: The Horn of Africa's Breakaway State." *Council on Foreign Relations*, 1 Feb. 2018, www.cfr.org/backgrounder/somaliland-horn-africas-breakaway-state.
- Metz, Helen C. ed. "Siad Barre and Scientific Socialism", *Somalia: A Country Study*, Washington, D.C.1992: Library of Congress.

- MGoth. "Briefing Piper Somaliland Voter Cards Distribution." *Somaliland Press*, 3 Aug. 2017, www.somalilandpress.com/briefing-paper-somaliland-voter-cards-distribution/. Accessed 23 Nov. 2023.
- Mills, Greg, et al. "Somaliland: The Power of Democracy." *RUSI*, 4 June. 2021, www.rusi.org/explore-our-research/publications/commentary/somaliland-power-democracy. Accessed 23 Nov. 2023.
- O'Connell, David. "Disrupting Arms Trafficking in Somali Waters." *UNODC East African News and Stores*, 31 May 2023, www.unodc.org/easternafrika/en/Stories/disrupting-arms-trafficking-in-somali-waters-.html.
- Omenma, J. T., et al. "Al-Shabaab and Boko Haram: Recruitment Strategies." *Peace and Conflict Studies*, no. 10827307, 1980, <https://doi.org/10.46743/1082-7307/2020.1460>. Accessed 22 Nov. 2023.
- Phillips, Michael M. "China Fumes Over Somaliland'S Warm Ties With Taiwan Few African Regions Have the Nerve to Say No to China. Independence-minded Somaliland Is One." *The Wall Street Journal*, 11 Aug. 2022, www.wsj.com/articles/china-fumes-as-somaliland-refuses-to-unfriend-taiwan-11660213603.
- Renders, Marleen. *Consider Somaliland State-Building with Traditional Readers and Institutions*. vol. 26, Brill, 2012.
- "Somalia Situation Update: October 2023 | Al-Shabaab Strikes Back at Local Administrators." *ACLEDA*, 20 Oct. 2023, acleddata.com/2023/10/20/somalia-situation-update-october-2023-al-shabaab-strikes-back-at-local-administrators/. Accessed 21 Nov. 2023.
- "Somalia-Somaliland: A Halting Embrace of Dialogue." *Crisis Group*, 6 Aug. 2020, www.crisisgroup.org/africa/horn-africa/somalia/somalia-somaliland-halting-embrace-dialogue. Accessed 22 Nov. 2023.
- "Somalia: Somaliland Forces Take Control of Tukaraq." *GaroweOnline*, 1 Aug. 2018, www.garoweonline.com/en/news/puntland/somalia-somaliland-forces-take-control-of-tukaraq. Accessed 22 Nov. 2023.
- "Somali Dialects/Accent Map. Which One Do You Speak?" *The Somali Spot*, 18 Sept. 2020, <https://www.somalispot.com/threads/somali-dialects-accent-map-which-one-do-you-speak.96445/>.

"Somaliland, an Unrecognised State, Is Winning Friends Abroad." *The Economist*, 8 May 2021, www.economist.com/middle-east-and-africa/2021/05/06/somaliland-an-unrecognised-state-is-winning-friends-abroad.

"Somaliland Rejects Talk of Unification with Somalia After Museveni Comment." *AL JAZEERA AND NEWS AGENCIES*, 25 Sep. 2023.

"SSC-Khaatumo Declares Cessation of Conflict in Sool, Sanag, and Cayn Areas." *Hiiraan*, 29 Aug. 2023, hiiraan.com/news4/2023/Aug/192813/ssc_khatumo_declares_cessation_of_conflict_in_sool_sanag_and_cayn_areas.aspx.

Tellander, Ebba, and Mohamed A. Hassan. "Accountability in the Taxation System in Somaliland." *The Peace Research Institute Oslo*, 24 Jan. 2016, css.ethz.ch/content/dam/ethz/special-interest/gess/cis/center-for-securities-studies/resources/docs/PRIO-Accountability%20in%20the%20Taxation%20System%20in%20Somaliland.pdf.

The Ethiopian Revolution: War in the Horn of Africa. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press. ISBN 978-0-300-14163-4.

"Time for Somaliland and the Dhulbahante to Talk." *International Crisis Group*, 19 May 2023, www.crisisgroup.org/africa/horn-africa/somaliland/time-somaliland-and-dhulbahante-talk

UNDP, *Human Development Report 2001-Somalia*, (New York: 2001), p. 42